

Matric Deformations and Space Travel via Compact Topological Spaces – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

The 8T framework consist of the three equations – the coupling constant equation, which regard bosonic fields as net curvature on a Lorentz manifold. Net curvature are represented in prime numbers. The theory predicted the value of the fine structure constant by using the weak interaction coupling constant. The formation of the coupling constant equation is presented in the sequence of equations (1)-(1.3). The time invariant acceleration, which describe the phenomena of dark energy, and the quark masses series. This paper will analyze the main two equation regarding to space travel in effective time via compact topological spaces attainable to access from every point on the matric.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.3)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \quad (1.4)$$

In the 8-theory framework, the Quarks are arbitrary variations of a Lorentz manifold. Those vanish into matter. We covered this idea in depth in previous papers, but never analyzed the shape of one of those things, called Quarks. How would a quark look in this framework? Of course, that is just an idea, but in this framework, quarks are extreme amount of curvature, they Are not separate entity, but part of the manifold itself, a curvature of the manifold, which must be eliminated, that is precisely the reason they form the SO (3) group. That is why we regard atoms and matter, stars and Galaxies, endless succession of arbitrary variation elimination, given to us by the second equation. So quarks are actually resemble the Dirac delta, or a hyperbole in space, we only see the top of the hyperbole so to us it looks flat. The fact that we can move from family to family using the third Equation means that it is the same hyperbole but different heights. Just like a harmonic motion with damping, where it is the same frequency but decreasing amplitude.

What if we could cross the barrier of the third family with the highest mass? Alternatively, in the 8-theory what if we create an immense amount of energy on the metric, well beyond the masses of the third Family. What will happen then? That is synonymous to creating an immense amount of curvature on the manifold. According to the first equation we are going to transition to the topological realm, which keeps the manifold stationary, given by the fourth term of that equation. However, we are on the metric itself how can we move to the realm of topology, which stay as it is over time and cover the entire space, i.e. it's compact. We have two options, either an instantaneous jump from the manifold to the topology or a gate opening between the metric space and the topological space; we will see space no longer generate energy, it will retain its original shape. Just itself ripped apart. Then after we another predication by the 8-theory.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Notice that the terms in equation 2.1 are not dependent upon the metric, they are purely topological. It validates the idea that there is an underlining space, which is completely separate from the metric. Such a space is not dependent upon coordinate and as equation (2) suggest could be accessible from every point given high enough energy. Instead of maneuvering in space from a starting point to an endpoint, it is possible to access the compact topological space, and as it covers every point on the metric space, shift again to the metric by lowering the energy. Notice that the first three terms are perfectly describing the universe we are living in, an expanding metric, which vary according to a varying topology. The 8-theory is really an expansion of GR so the result is a GR with fermions and bosons, i.e. a unified theory, supported by the coupling constant series. The old fashion way of space travel is linear; calculate the distance from the start to the end on the metric, given by equation (2.2). The 8-theory suggest a different method, given by equation (2.30):

$$ST: M_{x1,y1,z1} \rightarrow M_{x2,y2,z2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$8T: M_{x1,y1,z1} \rightarrow g \quad (2.30)$$

$$8T^{-1}: g \rightarrow M_{x2,y2,z2} \quad (2.31)$$

Such a space is connected to the metric, by equation (2), and by satisfying condition (2.1) there will be a transition to the topology, which could be associated with physical features of high energy, such as blue shifts. Exciting times ahead indeed. A prediction of the 8 theory that in high energy, a ripping apart of the metric space will be manifested. A shifting to the topology can be made by the other extreme, minimal amount of energy. If we accept the moment organism death as the moment of lowest energy, there should be a shift to a topological space at that moment as well. In fact, many organisms, which had near death experience, describe a shift to a space, which is highly resemble in traits to a compact topological space.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)